

PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE AS A DETERMINING FACTOR OF PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF FUTURE OFFICERS

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RESUME

This article is devoted to the topic of professional competence as a factor determining the professional maturity of future officers. Pedagogical and psychological aspects of officer personnel training are covered in the article. In particular, the issues of pedagogical conditions, laws, specific types of competence that form professional competence are covered in detail.

Key words: State, Armed Forces, military service, military discipline, officer, professional training, professional competence, cadet, chief, commander, military pedagogy, military psychology.

It is known that all disciplines have contributed and adding to the development of military sectors. It should be noted that science achievements will serve to facilitate the person and increase the efficiency. It is self-aware that as all subjects are directly against individuals and its activities, an important science is also considered an important science in the study of the laws of the military sphere. The results of the military research in the field of pedagogy are natural to directly implement in the field of military services. This is also a key servictory of the huge surgeries in the field of self-defense. In this respect, this problem is very important in the study.

In the process of service, the next unexpected former can face unexpected conditions, only a specialist or head of department with special practical pedagogical and psychological knowledge. The head of the department has the opportunity to solve. This situation is associated with the issue of self-professional competence, which is the only system of pedagogical and psychological knowledge of the future officer.

The work of high-level formation of professional competence of future officers includes, in its content, issues such as guaranteeing the protection of the homeland, ensuring military security and solving the problems of reforming the Armed Forces. In the conditions of globalization, the work of fully ensuring the security of the homeland's borders is increasing the demands for the profession of military personnel.

In this regard, the professional and psychological training of future officers and their rational service activities in extreme conditions are being rapidly improved.

The new requirements for the activities of military personnel aim at the professional training of subjects, as well as the use of innovative pedagogical and psychological methods of training in higher military educational institutions.

In this regard, officer pedagogues working at the higher military educational institution are also doing remarkable work. Pedagogical, psychological, sociological, legal, philosophical and historical aspects of military activity are comprehensively studied by them. Here it is very important to pay attention to the pedagogical aspects of the problem.

Professional knowledge and skills are very important in the training of future officers, and it is necessary to explain this with the concept of professional competence. As reasons for studying this issue. The following are distinguished in military pedagogy[1,125].

1. Rapid changes in modern society, the high rate of socio-economic changes in it creates a number of requirements for professional responsibility, which further increases the importance of the process of mastering professional knowledge;
2. The requirements of military service and the increasing need of society for highly qualified military specialists, as well as the tasks of modernizing the military-professional education system;
3. Activity, independence, i.e. the readiness of military personnel to perform their duties, the issue of the ability to successfully solve various tasks of military activity;
4. The issue of professional military personnel who do not wait for instructions in extreme conditions and successfully perform their duties from the day of their appointment, show creative and rational initiative, etc.

This means that it is advisable to use the concept of "Competence" in the concept of "professional preparation" in the modern military pedagogy. It is also the concept of competence in modern pedagogy in various means: [2,98]:

- Having a prisoner;
- Have knowledge to judge a situation;
- knowledge;
- An explainer is explained in a certain area as knowledge.

It follows that competence and skill are complementary and interrelated concepts.

Therefore, for the effective implementation of military activities, it is considered necessary for future officers to have professional skills.

V.S. According to Bezrukova, competence is the acquisition of knowledge and skills that allow to express qualified judgments, evaluations, opinions [2,112].

In contrast, O.N. Shakhmatov understands professional competence as a set of professional knowledge and skills, as well as methods of professional activity [2, 143].

In the dictionary of practical psychology, socio-psychological competence is also distinguished, and it is defined as the ability of a person to interact effectively in the system of interpersonal relations.

Professional competence is a set of personal abilities that reflect a certain level of competence and allow constructive action in changing social conditions.

The professional competence of the future officer should consist of such components as spiritual, moral, cognitive, creative, communicative.

The socio-psychological ability of a future officer is a system of special knowledge about society, politics, economy, culture, etc. In other words, it is the socio-psychological competence of the officer. It allows a person to act effectively in any social sphere, that is, to make the right decision in difficult situations and achieve goals, etc.

In contrast to the above, the essence of military professional competence is also manifested in the formation of a set of qualities among military personnel that meet the requirements of military service.

Military-professional competence means the ability and readiness to solve professional problems and tasks that arise in real situations of military operations based on the knowledge, skills, abilities, professional and life experience, and values of military personnel [3,98].

The system of special competences of future officers as a specialist, which is formed and developed during the training process, is determined.

Literally, military-professional competence is the professional training or ability of a soldier or future officer to perform combat tasks and duties in military service without difficulty.

Correspondingly, the concept of military professionalism is also complex and multifaceted, it combines several social goals and tasks in the service: combat training, professional and official activities, daily contacts. In this, the development of military groups is carried out and the results of military work are achieved. That is, combat training, moral and spiritual condition of cadets, discipline, etc. In this, a number of pedagogical and psychological qualities of the future officer related to the future management method, such as organizational, legal, disciplinary, are distinguished[4,7]:

-Planning and forecasting, making decisions, setting goals and tasks for performers;

- Organization and coordination of joint activities of subordinates and teams;
- Management and authorization;
- Formation of a positive psychological climate in the military team;
- Ability to exert psychological and socio-psychological influence on subordinates;
- Organization of maintenance of mental health of employees and prevention of mental and somatic diseases;
- Carrying out psychological work in the battalion - that is, providing psychological help to those who need it, as well as psychological diagnosis, monitoring psychodiagnostic work conducted by a military psychologist, etc. At this point, it is appropriate to pay attention to the concept of "Psychological competence".

Psychological competence is the ability to understand the functional-psychological and social-psychological knowledge and skills of soldiers, as well as certain personal qualities, which allows future officers to work individually with subordinates.

The psychological ability of a modern officer is one of the main components of military-professional competence. The content of this concept, that is, the professional activity of an officer in peacetime, is manifested in the responsibility of maintaining combat readiness, monitoring the successful performance of combat tasks by soldiers [5,93].

However, in some studies, information related to the psychological analysis of the Commander's activity is also prominent. Among the researchers M.I. Dyachenko, E.I. Osipenkova, L.E. Merzlyak distinguishes the unique pedagogical aspects of the activity of a military commander [6,82].

1. Socio-political;
2. Organizational and management;
3. Military special;
4. Military pedagogy;
5. Administrative and economic.

Of course, all these functions are very important in the activity of the commander.

In contrast to the above, in some studies in the field of military psychology, some characterological qualities are listed as a prerequisite for future officers;

1. Socio-ethical qualities: harmony of social and personal motives, social responsibility, sense of duty, accuracy and discipline in fulfilling obligations;

2. Intellectual qualities: speed, flexibility, independence and critical thinking, creative thinking, self-control;
3. Organizational and management qualities: demandingness, respect and courtesy to subordinates, faithfulness to the word, management, emotional and voluntary stability;
4. Communicative qualities: high and real self-awareness, self-confidence, self-awareness, self-respect, sense of humor, literacy, clarity and expressiveness of speech, etc.

In short, the level of psychological ability is the main condition for the future officer's professional and psychological training.

Therefore, in all areas, including the military, psychological ability is considered an important psychological criterion for team management, organization and training. Also, it is natural that the phenomenon of psychological competence, which is formed in future officers, serves as one of the pedagogical and psychological factors that ensure the dynamics of their future professional development.

Used literature:

1. Biochinsky I.V. Organizational and pedagogical foundations of the professional training of an officer in a military university. Abstract of the dissertation of Dr. ped. Sciences. Kazan, 1993.
2. Military pedagogical diagnostics: theory and practice// A short course of lectures on social pedagogy. M.: VU, 1996.
3. Tarasenko A.V. Psychological foundations of the manager's optimal managerial activity. Monograph - M.: Ed. Soyuz, 2009.
4. Kovalenko A.V. Professionalism of subjects of psychological work of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Kazakhstan and directions of its development// Collection of scientific articles of adjuncts of the Military University (DSP). - M.: VU, 2009. - Issue 12. - P. 52-72.
5. Questions of training and education in military schools / Under. Ed. I.N. Shkadova.- M., 1976. - P. 26.
6. M.I. Dyachenko, E.F. Osipenkov, L.E. Merzlyak. Psychological and pedagogical bases of the commander's activity. - M., 1977. - P. 8.

